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Ethnicity, Language, and Work Segregation: A Cohesive and Profitability Perspective

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Abstract

This research aims to obtain the benefit of the organization in the work place, the employee cohesiveness and positive perspectives could be focus on some various factors such as; cultural differences, (ethnicity), language differences and injustice over the separation of one group from other in the workplace (exclusion). The purpose of the research that carried out qualitatively. The approach in this research is descriptive method by using this descriptive method is to describe whether cultural differences (Ethnicity), differences in language (Language) and different treatment of employees in the work environment (Workplace Segregation) have an effect on good or bad employee cohesiveness. (A Cohesive) in carrying out its main duties and inherent functions and how it affects the employee's perspective on his ability to bring benefits to himself and his organization (Profitability Perspective). Based on the research model framework the researcher concludes 16 research hypotheses that Ethnicity, language, work segregation has positive effects toward employee's cohesiveness and profitability perspectives. But Gender can have positive and negative effects toward Interpersonal Attractive.

Keywords: Ethnicity, Language, Work Segregation, Cohesiveness and Profitability Perspective

1. Introduction

Something that applies globally in achieving the goals of an organization that one of them is achieved through the fulfillment of a determining asset in one of the resources is Human Resources. An organization really needs to understand and tolerate the differences in its employees in order to create a good work climate with mutual respect so that it has an impact on work cohesiveness, employee perspectives to increase their potential and productivity in an effort that bring more benefits to the organization

In Indonesia, employee cohesiveness and positive perspectives could benefit themselves and their organizations are often influenced by various factors such as cultural differences (ethnicity), language differences and injustice over the separation of one group from another employee (exclusion) in the workplace. Because this fact have an impact on the cohesiveness of employees in carrying out their main tasks and functions and reduce the perspective of employees' abilities on potential that can increase self and organizational profitability, so it is necessary to

observe and research these conditions as an effort to prevent negative conditions and efforts. improving the quality of human resources for an organization.

The various differences mentioned above are often encountered by organizations as several forms of problems such as cultural differences that often the basis for employee behavior and courage in terms of different decision making, differences in language acquisition and minimum understanding often result in limited communication and understanding of employee duties, unfair treatment of employees (segregation) in the workplace often results in the development of employees' potential and creativity as well as the lack of employee cohesiveness and the Human Resource's perspective to be able to benefit themselves and the organization because they are not fully accommodated and understood by the organization.

Therefore, the purpose of research that carried out qualitatively with this descriptive method is to describe whether cultural differences (Ethnicity), differences in language (Language) and different treatment of employees in the work environment (Workplace Segregation) have an effect on good or bad employee cohesiveness. (A Cohesive) in carrying out its main duties and inherent functions and how it affects the employee's perspective on his ability to bring benefits to himself and his organization (Profitability Perspective). The approach in this descriptive method is through the exposure of several literature reviews on previous journal research and then draw a final conclusion in accordance with these objectives.

2. Literature Review and Research Model Framework

Figure 1: Research Model framework

Source: author

Based on the Research Model framework above, then obtained 16 research hypotheses which will determine whether the relationship is significant or not between the variables. Those hypotheses include:

- H1 : Ethnicity affects toward A Cohesive of an organization
- H2 : Language affects toward A Cohesive of an organization
- H3 : Workplace Segregation affects toward A Cohesive of an organization
- H4 : Ethnicity affects toward Profitability Perspective of an organization
- H5 : Language affects toward Profitability Perspective of an organization
- H6 : Workplace Segregation affects toward Profitability Perspective of an organization
- H7 : Internal Control affects toward Interpersonal Individual Attraction
- H8 : Internal Control affects toward Maximizing income individual of an organization
- H9 : External Control affects toward Interpersonal Individual Attraction
- H10 : External Control affects toward Maximizing individual income of an organization
- H11 : Linguistic Resource affects toward Interpersonal Individual Attraction of an organization.
- H12 : Linguistic Resource affects toward Maximizing individual income of an organization
- H13 : Gender affects toward Interpersonal Attraction of an organization
- H14 : Gender affects toward maximizing individual income of an organization
- H15 : Social Skill affects toward Interpersonal Attraction of an organization
- H16 : Social Skill affects toward Maximizing individual income of an organization

The explanation of the whole hypothesis above will be summarized in the following sub-themes:

2.1. Culture (Ethnicity) in organization environment

Culture is formed in every country and it is handed down from generation to generation to each generation as a way of life that is owned and develops according to the times. Because culture is a pattern of life that is comprehensive, complex, abstract and very broad, many aspects of culture also determine the communicative behavior of a person or group of people in an organization.

The word Ethnicity means attachment to the cultural value system of a particular group on the same ethnics, national origin, religion / belief or a combination of these categories. Value has an element of consideration which contains a person's ideas or ideas about things that are good, true or desired. Value is a tool that shows in principle that the process of execution or a certain final state that is socially preferable.

By category, cultural (ethnic) differences are not always influenced by the presence or absence/existence of physical relationships between these ethnic groups. Even though there has been cultural penetration between several different ethnic groups, the boundaries of each culture still persist. These original cultural boundaries make the characteristics that become the cultural identity of each ethnicity in a country. Cultural identity is a role attribute that is internal and external and often used in the interaction process. So that it can be stated that the cultural identity of a society in a nation also influences the various patterns of the order of the values of the community's life.

The differences in values, rules and beliefs in the social life of society vary according to ethnic diversity which has an impact on different desires and behavior of a person (Luo, 2009). This is also supported by the opinion of Scholtens and Dam (2007) which states that there are real differences in corporate ethics policies that are applied and centered on different countries. Lozano (1998) also concludes the same result in his research that culture (ethnicity) contributes to the dominant value of a business activity. The results of research by Goerge et al. (2012) also state that organizational culture is also influenced by national culture, so that it should be a concern for a multinational organization when planning to Go Global and operate in other countries. An organization should have a profitability perspective by making adjustments to the local culture at each of its business locations. Culture as an external factor in the work environment plays a role in determining the success or failure of the business. For example, making decisions on products to be produced must be adjusted to local wisdom in the area where the business is built so that it will be in line with the acceptance of market share and the profit from sales. Based on several reviews on the results of previous research in several journals above, it is concluded that internal control

(habit) and external control (value) have an influence on cultural diversity (Ethnicity) and the profitability perspective in this case is the effort to maximize income. **So, it can be said that Hypothesis 4, Hypothesis 8 and Hypothesis 10 are accepted.**

A certain area that has multi-ethnicity become very strong with the integration of cultures with each other or contrarily became weak (divided) if negative effects are found on the cohesiveness and mutual trust that fades between cultures. It was because separated areas can provide fewer opportunities for more meaningful social interaction between groups of people and tend to strengthen their respective ethnic identities and social contacts within certain groups in different social environments (Rothwell, 2012). **This statement supports hypothesis 1, that ethnicity affects A Cohesive.**

The question of the positive or negative effects of ethnic differences on cohesiveness (Cohesion) yields two different theories. Tajfel (1981) states that the first perspective is the "Conflict Theory" which states that various social environments cause feelings of discomfort and anxiety between minority and majority groups including in an organization mainly as a result of competition for limited resources, besides that because of social identity status and position, relative in the hierarchy of power which also determines the degree which group members work together to achieve organizational goals. Those threats create stereotypical characteristics and discriminatory treatment of different ethnic groups.

Differently, "Contact Theory" states that stereotypical characteristics and prejudice can be reduced through direct relationships between individuals and members of different ethnic groups. Basically, direct relationships of various members of ethnic groups have been shown to reduce various negative attitudes and behavioral measures in the group (Pettigrew and Tropp, 2006). It is because stereotypes are replaced by other schemes that derive from direct individual experience and serve as a reason for the heterogeneity of individuals within and between different ethnic groups. The level of positive individual interaction in general into their ethnic group as well as outside their ethnic group results in the loss of prejudice between individuals and also conflicts between different ethnic groups.

In general conditions, contact theory has a positive effect on the same ethnic group even when the relationship or contact is experienced through delegation or representation, networks of friends from other friends, work partners and even family (Wright et al., 1997). Ford (2008) proved that in the UK age is very influential on negative racial attitudes, the racial prejudice attitude of young age groups who grow up in communities with various ethnicities is very small. And in Canada, Stole and Harell (2012) did not find general trust in young age groups with multi-ethnic networks of friends, instead finding greater trust between ethnically diverse neighbors. **Those five opinions in the previous review indicate the truth of Hypothesis 7, that Internal Control affects Interpersonal Attraction.**

Sturgis et al. (2011) showed a positive and strong interaction relationship between cultural diversity, contacts / relationships and trust (values) between members of ethnic groups. According to him, the Contact theory and the Conflict theory in general have different mechanisms, but in certain environments, the two mechanisms may occur simultaneously. For example, in a multi-ethnic environment it may be that some individuals feel anxious about feeling threatened or prejudice against others, but on the other hand it could be the opposite, which results in positive attitudes towards different ethnic groups. As a determinant of the individual's attitude as external control in an ethnically diverse environment is the level of social contact and meaningful interaction between these individuals.

A study of Sturgis et al. (2014) states that ethnic diversity and segregation have an effect on social cohesion in the environment which is very clearly influenced by individual age factors, ethnic diversity has two effects, a positive effect on social cohesion for young people but on the contrary has a negative and there is a tendency for social cohesiveness in the older age group. The reason for these two effects is due to the difference in the level of trust and active interaction in the cohesion of the interpersonal community.

The positive effect of a relationship or contact between group members will appear greater if it has several additional requirements, among others, if members within or between groups have the same status, if group identity

is dominant, when group members are oriented towards achieving on common goals and if a relationship between groups / contacts supported by social institutions (Pettigrew, 1998). **Some of these statements support Hypothesis 9, that external control has an effect on Interpersonal Attraction.**

2.2 Language in organization

With regard to the work environment and its relationship with language, there has been an increase in skepticism about the use of language from certain countries in another country in understanding daily communication practices (Blommaert, 2010). In order to create a communicative impression in daily face-to-face communication characterized by contacts between individuals who come from different cultural backgrounds, linguistic resources are needed (Blommaert, 2011). Individuals who come from other countries should understand the practice of communicating with the National Language that is applied in that country. Mastery over languages of other countries where an individual who comes from a different country will provide more value in interacting and communicating formally and informally.

According to Bloomfield, L. (1933) Language as a communication tool means that language is a series of systematic sounds, in the form of symbols, arbitrary, meaningful, conventional, unique, universal, productive, varied, dynamic, human, and a means of social interaction that replaces individuals in stating something or expressing to the interlocutor. in a social group as a means of communication and the identity of the speaker. Language as a thought image means that language is formed from thoughts, or the form of language (individually and spontaneously) imitates or follows the form of thoughts or ideas.

In the concept of language, there is the concept of diversity. The term of Superdiversity concept was developed to meet broader communicative needs in diversity studies which include multimodal aspects of communication such as movement, posture, use of space, how text is represented on a signboard and so on. Historical antecedents explain what unites certain people and how superdiversity can be created as strength and cohesiveness of an organization and nation through development (Arnaut et al., 2015). **Then Hypothesis 2 is fulfilled.**

Zane Goebel (2018) sees a unity and pure perspective. Language in general in Indonesia is increasingly mixed by linguistic shifts that come from other languages and social changes that occurred. Local and foreign people tolerate each other and try to master the language that guides interpersonal communication in everyday life and in their work environment. Indonesian citizens in an effort to adapt to the era of globalization and self-awareness as the Asean Economic Community are now making English a second language that must be understood and be mastered in addition to Indonesian as their mother tongue. This is understood as a form of the profitability perspective of the community to be more advanced and develop the potential for success and to achieve benefits in terms of employment and income. Through mastery of a foreign language, a person is able to adapt to the progress of the world and open horizons and work in multi-field and multinational corporations around the world. **Those assumptions in Hypothesis 5 are accepted.**

Variations of colloquial ethnic languages and mixed languages acquire social value in many social domains in Indonesia. The consequences of this language shift led to increased familiarity with the multiethnic fragments of language and allowed interaction and understanding of the meaning of the language of several Indonesian societies with different cultures. Now, in general, fragments of ethnic languages are felt in the Indonesian-speaking National narrative. Agha (2007) talks about how the language fragments used allow people involved in interaction to understand each other with ideas about language that are generated by state institutions. For example, in interacting between different ethnicities on the island of Java, non-Javanese ethnicities can use Javanese fragments to harmonize with community ideas (Goebel, 2010). **The statements in this paragraph support the content of Hypothesis 11.**

The results of Zane Goebel's research (2018) show that changes in the idea of language are revalued and can be found in every situation that involves various types of communication. Everything related to Indonesian culture continues that to be configured in view of future perspectives through profitable processes and projects, such as the television industry which has become a medium of information and communication to benefit Indonesian

people in all regions. These processes of change have contributed to further diversification of Indonesia through the positive revaluation of previously neglected local language varieties. **The statement of the results of this study supports Hypothesis 12.**

2.3 Different Treatment (Segregation) in organization

A condition of separation (one class from another) can cause feelings of alienation or isolation in the workplace. Uslaner (2010,2012) and Rothwell (2012) argue that the tendency to dominate ethnicity and diversity has caused real failure in organizations and has an impact on segregation in the work environment. Only about 3% of segregation due to differences in race at work is due to the level of education between black and white employee groups, but most ethnic segregation (32%) in the workplace is due to differences in language proficiency (Hellerstein, 2006). In contrast to the title of this study, Hellerstein's previous research made differences in language proficiency and race as independent variables. Other differences that can also cause segregation in the workplace are Gender and Social Skills. All the differences that exist cause the effect of segregation on individual cohesion or feelings of clinging which have an impact on cohesiveness in the work environment and one's perspective on being able to work in an effort to achieve more benefits for oneself and contributions to the organization. **Then Hypothesis 3 and Hypothesis 6 are accepted.**

Lee Cinthia (2004) found that a person's past performance and self-efficacy had a positive relationship with group efficacy. Efficacy here means a belief in the ability to organize, perform a task, achieve goals and final results and implement actions to achieve a form of skill. Furthermore, it is said that the interaction of gender diversity and group efficiency is positively related to group effectiveness as seen from the creation of group cohesion and project achievement. In particular, groups consisting of members of mixed gender facilitates the link between the efficiency of the group and the effectiveness of the group. Williams and O'Reilly (1998) note that there is provisional evidence obtained about a greater effect of gender, race, ethnicity, age or years of service on job effectiveness or less observable (education, functional background, background). Research on gender shows that the more homogeneous the group's gender composition, the higher their job satisfaction (Konrad et al., 1992). In addition, group cohesion is seen to be lower and conflict will be higher in mixed-gender groups (Kirchmeyer, 1995).

Furthermore, Williams and O'Reilly (1998) stated that the results of a number of studies revealed heterogeneity in race and gender often had a negative effect on group processes and performance. This is because an employee will feel more satisfied if he can work with other people who are considered to have the same attitude (Jackson et al., 1991). Therefore, from the perspective of attraction (equality), mixed gender groups are deemed ineffective due to the lack of opportunities to be interested in working together interpersonal (Byrne, 1971). Some of the negative realities of mixed gender groups are the frequent lack of positive attitudes, lack of active communication, and the possibility of high turnover of the group (Jehn et al., 1997).

The results of research that contradicts the role of gender on cohesion (cohesion) in the work group are presented by Field and Blum (1997) in the United States who found that job satisfaction is related to gender composition. They found that men and women working in gender-balanced groups found more job satisfaction than those in homogeneous work groups. Heterogeneous working groups will have an impact on increasing social interaction between members of the minority and majority, therefore according to Konrad et al. (1992) it is important to improve the relationship between group members and reduce the differences between subgroups (male or female). Blum (1984) suggests that due to the larger number of women in the workforce and the greater level of intimacy among them, this potential can lead to the achievement of more positive employment outcomes.

According to Ancona (1993) there are two important components of group performance, namely task performance and group maintenance. In order for a work group to be successful, they must complete pre-assigned tasks and also manage an interpersonal work environment, keeping it harmonious and conflict free. In addition to objective task performance, work group maintenance can also be measured through members' positive feelings about group interactions or members' interpersonal interest in the group so as to create cohesion (group cohesion). High group efficiency such as group cohesion can increase the likelihood of group thinking and limit members' independent

critical thinking so that it may affect poor group decision-making outcomes. It is possible that perceptions of collective efficiency and consent seeking behavior are more likely to occur in the same gender group because they may have the same attitudes (Jackson et al., 1991). The findings suggest that the interaction of gender diversity and group efficiency is responsible for group performance but may not be cohesion, but the interaction of gender diversity suggests a strong direction. **Based on the several research results on the pros and cons of the role of gender on interpersonal attraction (cohesion), it can be concluded that Hypothesis 13 is accepted.**

Gender characteristics often explain the differences in terms of obtaining successful income / income. Some of these unsuccessful factors are caused by the smaller size of the women's business, women's inexperience, their unfavorable and profitable concentration in the industry as well as the structural weaknesses of women both inside and outside the business arena. Women seem to prefer the small business arena to avoid well-documented labor losses (Fox & Hesse –Biber, 1984). However, their businesses are not as successful as those of men, even when women operate in the same industry (Loscocco & Robinson, 1991). There are several reasons that may be the cause of relatively women experiencing financial inadequacy in business. This can be broadly categorized as a function of the individual differences brought to the small business sector. Thus differences in material resources such as financial and human capital brought into the business arena may be largely responsible for gender differences in economic success (Light, 1984).

The issue of gender equality in the field of employment is still widely discussed in various countries, including in Indonesia. Although various protections have been sought through international and national legal products, the cultural background in a country will still play an important role in efforts to achieve gender equality in the field of employment (Nuraeni and Suryono 2021).

On the previous studies on women and small businesses have tended to assess women's motivation to choose small and medium enterprises. The results of previous studies show that women are actually similar in motivation for men to start their own businesses, although women are more likely to join the ownership business as a response to the lack of opportunities in the labor market (Bender, 1980). Women as business owners are actually the same as male business partners, tend to have internal locus of control or beliefs to determine their own destiny and tend to respect autonomy and achievement (Cromie, 1987). The differences in character and personality between female and male business owners are known, the pattern does not indicate that women are less suitable to be business owners (Smith et al., 1982).

According to the traditional perspective, gender differences in work outcomes are expected to be able to explain that before entering a certain job position both women and men have had dissemination, training and other experiences that are different and ultimately shape their experiences about work (McCreary, 1987). In line with the traditional perspective, the gender model states that the failure of women as business owners is comparable to that of men in terms of lack of human resources. In fact, women reported that they lacked the managerial and technical skills essential to the success of their businesses (Humphreys & McClung, 1981). Marini & Brinton (1984) stated that gender differences in socialization experiences can result in women having less attitudes such as risk-taking and internal locus of control which are considered important for business success.

According to Loscocco (2016), there are two important ways of investigation in the study of gender and business success. First, it is important to ascertain which factors are identified that most explain the causes of the lower tendency of women to achieve economic success in business than men. While the gender model emphasizes personal characteristics, the job model identifies aspects of the work-related structure as the main determinants of work outcomes. Second, it is also important to assess whether the various individual and structural determinants go through in the same or different processes in influencing the economic success of women or men as business owners.

The idea of the process is different for women and men that consistent with the gender model of work. The unique socialization experiences of women and their different positions in the social structure can be very meaningful. Structural or occupational models, on the other hand, it is explaining that any gender differences in results can be

due to differences in individual and business characteristics. The implication is that if a woman shares male characteristics, then they will achieve a comparable level of success.

The essence of all the explanations for the last research is that in order to achieve success, everyone can have a profitability perspective regardless of gender and have the same chance of success. The way to achieve this is by increasing specific experience in business and industry, being able to manage goals and personal life well, have an entrepreneurial orientation, strive to achieve the same structural position regardless of gender, and strive to gain trust and expansion capital. **Based on these conclusions, Hypothesis 14 is not rejected.**

According to Gooderhama et al. (2004), cooperation tends to induce and is due to mutual assistance, exchange of needed resources and trust with others. Conversely, competition tends to cause and be induced by obstruction of each other's success, coercive and threatening tactics, increasing power differences, forced communication and the desire to win over others. The use of appropriate social skills is able to promote the success of other group members and requires them to have interpersonal skills in interaction with other groups in the work environment in terms of high-quality collaboration and have the motivation to continue to do their best. (DW Johnson, 2003). Based on the above opinion, a person should have social skills to be able to support his interpersonal skills when he interacts with other parties both in his daily life and in an effort to create cohesion in his work environment. **Thus, Hypothesis 15 can be accepted.**

In the results of the study of Mesch et al. (1988) regarding the long-term implementation of collaborative efforts, it was found that the combination of interdependence associated with positive goals allows better performance for all group members, and that having social skills will add to the highest level of achievement and productivity of group members of an organization. Archer-Kath et al. (1994) argued that providing individual feedback to someone on how often they engage in targeted social skills more effectively will be able to increase group member achievement and create more positive relationships within the group. By understanding the two opinions of the results of previous research, it can be said that a person will be able to realize his profitability perspective if he has social skills in interacting both individually and in groups in the workplace environment, **so that Hypothesis 16 can be accepted.**

2.3 Cohesiveness meaning (A Cohesive) in an organization

Cohesiveness is termed the creation of cohesiveness in the organization, the extent of employees are close to become a single unit who can present themselves in various ways and differences that are owned and can help each other towards the same end result. The basics of cohesiveness that must be possessed by employees include, among others, the existence of interpersonal attraction, the existence of structural integration and the ownership of attitudes that are shared by group members to be able to work together to achieve certain goals / tasks.

The employees cohesiveness can be realized through the existence of togetherness and intensive mutual interaction between fellow members of the organization. When employees have cohesiveness or cohesivity, they will feel protected so that communication becomes smoother and flexible.

Perspective is a person's point of view and perspective on something. Through the existing perspective of the employees of an organization, it will provide them with schemes or instructions regarding which point of view they will choose and use as meaning for the objects they want to achieve. Profitability perspective is an individual's perspective on their ability to benefit themselves and their organization (Ardianto and Q-Anees, 2014).

2.4 The meaning of employees have the perspectives to get the profits (Perspective Probability) in organization Meaning Employees have a Perspective to Get Profits (Perspective Probability) in the Organization.

3. Method

This study uses content analysis as a methodology. By using qualitative content analysis, this study focuses on the characteristics of language as communication by paying attention to the content or contextual meaning of texts or

literature (Budd, et.al, 1967). The aim of content analysis is “to provide knowledge and understanding of the phenomenon under study” (Downe, 1992). In this case, the study is related to the importance of Ethnicity, Language, and Work Segregation in Profitability Perspective.

4. Discussions

Based on the purpose of writing this study, it can be described that some of the results of the qualitative analysis through a literature review related to the title of the research we took “***Ethnicity, Language, Workplace Segregation: A Cohesive and Profitability Perspective***” as follow:

4.1 Ethnicity (Culture) through the indicators of Internal Control (Human Habitat) and External Controls (Cultural Values) have a significant influence on A Cohesive.

A Cohesive or a unified feeling in the form of unity / cohesiveness between individuals with one another both in everyday life and in organizations. The intimacy between individuals in the unity can be displayed in various ways and differences by frequently interacting and helping each other towards the achievement of the final goal. However, cohesiveness and trust can fade due to isolated opportunities for interaction due to the distance between regions that are far apart and people tend to be ethnocentric in the strength of their respective cultural identities.

4.2 Ethnicity also affect toward Profitability Perspective.

An organization must be wise in its viewpoint if it wants to develop a business or Go Global Organization by trying to respect the local cultural wisdom of a country. Various aspects should be of concern such as a variety of local resources that will be used as business assets, including human resources, raw material resources, understanding cultural habits related to market share and values or different local policy rules in various country of origin that must be respected.

4.3 Internal Control Indicator of ethnicity also affects toward Interpersonal Attraction.

Where in general the results of previous research show that cultural diversity provides an attraction between fellow members of the organization or individual to cooperate and interact in a compact manner. In general, there are two theories in the relationship between Ethnicity and Cohesion, the first is Conflict Theory where interpersonal interactions cause anxiety / conflict due to limited resources, differences in identity status and relative positions in the hierarchy of power so that it impacts on differences in the degree of individuals working together to achieve organizational goals and the second is Contact Theory, which means that the intensity of a strong interpersonal contact relationship will directly reduce a person's negative prejudice and stereotypical characteristics.

4.4 External Control Indicator of ethnicity also affect toward Interpersonal Attraction.

Where the differences in values, rules and beliefs in the social life of people of different ethnic diversity will have an impact on differences in individual behavior and desires.

4.5 Internal Control Indicator affects toward Maximizing Income.

It shown through the Habit of individuals who always want to interact, cooperate more widely across their borders and collaborate with foreign parties even though it is risky to develop the potential of themselves and the organization in an effort to increase profits such as income.

4.6 External Control Indicator affects toward Maximizing Income.

The rules, customary beliefs and cultural values serve as a fence to preserve the identity value of a country. So that efforts to obtain individual progress and organizational efforts must wisely see and support local wisdom which is the basic rule. When a person or an organization wants to go international, what is no less important is

the ability to adapt to the local culture of the place where we are. Organizations can do this by exporting products or importing raw materials, or conducting direct investment by opening branches or factories directly in other countries or in other areas using indigenous people as their human resources. This will have an impact on the reciprocal relationship between the people who get a job so that their standard of living increases and provides benefits to the organization due to the maximum increase in income and profit as long as the condition continues to flexibly follow the rules, values, and local cultural beliefs.

4.7 Language affects toward a Cohesiveness.

Language affects the strength of togetherness or cohesiveness of a group of individuals in society or a group of members in an organization (Cohesion). Good language mastery is able to make interpersonal and group communication smooth. Adaptation to the mastery and understanding of the meaning contained in the National Language of a country becomes an added value to be comfortable and feel accepted in a general community group or organization.

4.8 Language also affects toward Profitability Perspective.

An individual or an organization always thinks about adapting to the mastery and understanding of a foreign language which is dominant to become the mother tongue in a country or a typical regional language is used as the identity of the area before developing themselves and their organizations. If the local native language has been mastered, it will smoothen every activity and plan to achieve future goals such as developing a business by opening a branch office or taking education and even a career in another country. An organization will also get more benefits if it employs local native personnel of a region or country where a branch office is opened, this is because labor costs will be reduced, but human resource management must be adjusted to the use of the native language of the country or at least master of the language.

4.9 Linguistic Resource Indicators of Language affect toward interpersonal attractive.

Ethnic language variations and mixed languages in the interpersonal attractive of everyday life have dominated social circles, one of which is in Indonesia. This shift in language (linguistic power) results in increased familiarity with multiethnic language fragments in the National narrative, allowing interaction and understanding of the meaning of different regional languages among Indonesians of different ethnicities

4.10 Linguistic Resource Indicators of Language affect toward Maximizing Income.

The results of past research have shown the changes in language ideas that are revalued in nature and can be found in every situation involving various types of communication, both verbal and non-verbal. Everything related to Indonesian culture continues to be configured to see beneficial perspectives in the future through various processes and projects that involve the role of Language.

4.11 Workplace Segregation affects toward A Cohesive.

All the differences that exist in individuals and may cause separation or feelings of isolation such as Gender, Age, Race, Language, Social Skills will have an impact on the cohesion or feelings of individual attachment to a sense of cohesiveness in interacting and cooperating with other people in their work environment.

4.12 Workplace Segregation affects toward Profitability Perspective.

It means that if a person feels separated from his work environment, psychologically it will have an impact on his inability to prove his true potential to achieve and perform better. Feelings of discomfort and exclusion will reduce one's perspective to work and achieve more benefits for oneself and the organization.

4.13 Gender can have positive and negative effects toward Interpersonal Attractive.

The influence of gender based on the results of previous research can be positive or negative on Interpersonal Attractive in the work environment. The research results can supported and stated that the more homogeneous the gender composition in a work group will increase the job satisfaction of members, it is because the members of these groups have the same attitude and enthusiasm for work. Meanwhile, the results of research that are contradictory to the heterogeneous gender composition will have an unfavorable impact on the satisfaction and performance of group members because group cohesion will appear to be lower and conflict will be higher in mixed gender groups. In addition, there is often a lack of good attitudes, passive communication and a tendency for high turnover of mixed gender groups. From all these reasons, the results of the contradictory research conclude that mixed gender groups are deemed ineffective because they are less able to cooperate interpersonally.

4.14 Gender affects toward Maximizing Income.

The results of previous research indicate that working groups consisting of mixed gender members specifically facilitate the relationship between group efficiency and group effectiveness in the organization. It can be concluded, in an effort to achieve success, everyone can have a positive view of achieving profitability regardless of gender differences because essentially have the same opportunities. Some of the ways to achieve this are through increasing experience in specific fields of business and industry, entrepreneurial orientation, being able to manage goals and personal life as well as possible and trying to gain the trust and business partners.

4.15 Social Skill affects toward Interpersonal Attractive.

A person should have the social skills to support his interpersonal skills when he interacts with other individuals in his daily life and in an effort to create cohesion and motivation to advance in his work environment.

4.16 Social Skill affects toward Maximizing Income

In the results of previous studies it was found that there was a combination of interdependence associated with positive goals enabling better performance for all group members of an organization. Having the expertise in social skills will also increase the level of achievement and productivity, which will lead to maximum income.

5. Conclusion

Based on the purpose of writing this study, it can be described that some of the results of the qualitative analysis through a literature review related to the title of the research we took "*Ethnicity, Language, Workplace Segregation: A Cohesive and Profitability Perspective*" as follow:

1. *Ethnicity* (Culture) through the indicators of Internal Control (Human Habitat) and External Controls (Cultural Values) have a significant influence on *A Cohesive*.
A Cohesive or a unified feeling in the form of unity / cohesiveness between individuals with one another both in everyday life and in organizations. The intimacy between individuals in the unity can be displayed in various ways and differences by frequently interacting and helping each other towards the achievement of the final goal. However, cohesiveness and trust can fade due to isolated opportunities for interaction due to the distance between regions that are far apart and people tend to be ethnocentric in the strength of their respective cultural identities.
2. *Ethnicity* also affect toward *Profitability Perspective*.
An organization must be wise in its viewpoint if it wants to develop a business or Go Global Organization by trying to respect the local cultural wisdom of a country. Various aspects should be of concern such as a variety of local resources that will be used as business assets, including human resources, raw material resources, understanding cultural habits related to market share and values or different local policy rules in various country of origin that must be respected.
3. Internal Control Indicator of *ethnicity* also affects toward *Interpersonal Attraction*.
Where in general the results of previous research show that cultural diversity provides an attraction between fellow members of the organization or individual to cooperate and interact in a compact manner.

In general, there are two theories in the relationship between Ethnicity and Cohesion, the first is **Conflict Theory** where interpersonal interactions cause anxiety / conflict due to limited resources, differences in identity status and relative positions in the hierarchy of power so that it impacts on differences in the degree of individuals working together to achieve organizational goals and the second is **Contact Theory**, which means that the intensity of a strong interpersonal contact relationship will directly reduce a person's negative prejudice and stereotypical characteristics.

4. External Control Indicator of *ethnicity* also affect toward *Interpersonal Attraction*.

Where the differences in values, rules and beliefs in the social life of people of different ethnic diversity will have an impact on differences in individual behavior and desires.

5. Internal Control Indicator affects toward *Maximizing Income*.

It shown through the Habit of individuals who always want to interact, cooperate more widely across their borders and collaborate with foreign parties even though it is risky to develop the potential of themselves and the organization in an effort to increase profits such as income.

6. External Control Indicator affects toward *Maximizing Income*.

The rules, customary beliefs and cultural values serve as a fence to preserve the identity value of a country. So that efforts to obtain individual progress and organizational efforts must wisely see and support local wisdom which is the basic rule. When a person or an organization wants to go international, what is no less important is the ability to adapt to the local culture of the place where we are. Organizations can do this by exporting products or importing raw materials, or conducting direct investment by opening branches or factories directly in other countries or in other areas using indigenous people as their human resources. This will have an impact on the reciprocal relationship between the people who get a job so that their standard of living increases and provides benefits to the organization due to the maximum increase in income and profit as long as the condition continues to flexibly follow the rules, values, and local cultural beliefs.

7. Language affects toward a Cohesiveness.

Language affects the strength of togetherness or cohesiveness of a group of individuals in society or a group of members in an organization (*Cohesion*). Good language mastery is able to make interpersonal and group communication smooth. Adaptation to the mastery and understanding of the meaning contained in the National Language of a country becomes an added value to be comfortable and feel accepted in a general community group or organization.

8. Language also affects toward *Profitability Perspective*.

An individual or an organization always thinks about adapting to the mastery and understanding of a foreign language which is dominant to become the mother tongue in a country or a typical regional language is used as the identity of the area before developing themselves and their organizations. If the local native language has been mastered, it will smoothen every activity and plan to achieve future goals such as developing a business by opening a branch office or taking education and even a career in another country. An organization will also get more benefits if it employs local native personnel of a region or country where a branch office is opened, this is because labor costs will be reduced, but human resource management must be adjusted to the use of the native language of the country or at least master of the language.

9. Linguistic Resource Indicators of Language affect toward *interpersonal attractive*.

Ethnic language variations and mixed languages in the interpersonal attractive of everyday life have dominated social circles, one of which is in Indonesia. This shift in language (linguistic power) results in increased familiarity with multiethnic language fragments in the National narrative, allowing interaction and understanding of the meaning of different regional languages among Indonesians of different ethnicities

10. Linguistic Resource Indicators of Language affect toward *Maximizing Income*.

The results of past research have shown the changes in language ideas that are revalued in nature and can be found in every situation involving various types of communication, both verbal and non-verbal. Everything related to Indonesian culture continues to be configured to see beneficial perspectives in the future through various processes and projects that involve the role of Language.

11. Workplace Segregation affects toward *A Cohesive*.

All the differences that exist in individuals and may cause separation or feelings of isolation such as Gender, Age, Race, Language, Social Skills will have an impact on the cohesion or feelings of individual attachment to a sense of cohesiveness in interacting and cooperating with other people in their work environment.

12. *Workplace Segregation affects toward Profitability Perspective.*

It means that if a person feels separated from his work environment, psychologically it will have an impact on his inability to prove his true potential to achieve and perform better. Feelings of discomfort and exclusion will reduce one's perspective to work and achieve more benefits for oneself and the organization.

13. *Gender can have positive and negative effects toward Interpersonal Attractive.*

The influence of gender based on the results of previous research can be positive or negative on *Interpersonal Attractive* in the work environment. The research results can supported and stated that the more homogeneous the gender composition in a work group will increase the job satisfaction of members, it is because the members of these groups have the same attitude and enthusiasm for work. Meanwhile, the results of research that are contradictory to the heterogeneous gender composition will have an unfavorable impact on the satisfaction and performance of group members because group cohesion will appear to be lower and conflict will be higher in mixed gender groups. In addition, there is often a lack of good attitudes, passive communication and a tendency for high turnover of mixed gender groups. From all these reasons, the results of the contradictory research conclude that mixed gender groups are deemed ineffective because they are less able to cooperate interpersonally.

14. *Gender affects toward Maximizing Income.*

The results of previous research indicate that working groups consisting of mixed gender members specifically facilitate the relationship between group efficiency and group effectiveness in the organization. It can be concluded, in an effort to achieve success, everyone can have a positive view of achieving profitability regardless of gender differences because essentially have the same opportunities. Some of the ways to achieve this are through increasing experience in specific fields of business and industry, entrepreneurial orientation, being able to manage goals and personal life as well as possible and trying to gain the trust and business partners.

15. *Social Skill affects toward Interpersonal Attractive.*

A person should have the social skills to support his interpersonal skills when he interacts with other individuals in his daily life and in an effort to create cohesion and motivation to advance in his work environment.

16. *Social Skill affects toward Maximizing Income*

In the results of previous study it was found that there was a combination of interdependence associated with positive goals enabling better performance for all group members of an organization. Having the expertise in social skills will also increase the level of achievement and productivity, which will lead to maximum income.

6. Suggestions

Several things that can be used as suggestions for improving the results of next research related to the same research theme, including:

1. The dependent variable indicators for ethnicity, language, and workplace segregation can be selected differently to be discussed further as an enrichment for the next literature review.
2. It is necessary to be examined and researched the level of work groups risks that are gender heterogeneous and gender homogeneous related to managerial decision making in organizations.
3. Future studies may need to examine the ways to find correct perceptions of the effectiveness of segregated teamwork, such as gender or age level.

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